

PROJECT SCOPE – Trademark Registration System

1. Overview

The project consists of the development of a system to support the trademark registration process. The system aims to enable the submission, analysis, and granting of trademark registrations by a public entity responsible for industrial property.

The system should support the main stages of the trademark lifecycle, including:

- evaluation of conflicts between registered trademarks and trademarks under application;
- formal and technical analysis performed by the examination team;
- decisions of approval, refusal, and archiving;
- generation of final grant documents and certificates.

2. Project Objective

The overall objective is to model and understand the complete trademark registration process, describing:

- **Activity flow**
 - from request submission to final decision.
- **Roles**
 - applicant, attorney/agent, examiner, and regulator.
- **Business rules**
 - formal criteria, trademark classification, analysis guidelines, and deadlines.
- **Resulting artifacts**
 - technical report, decision notice, and registration certificate.

3. Functional Scope

The system must encompass the following main functionalities:

3.1. Application Submission

- Create a new trademark registration request.
- Attach documents.
- Calculate and record mandatory information.
- Validate form completion using either free-text input or predefined specifications.

3.2. Protocol and Preliminary Analysis

- Record protocol date and time.
- Verify document completeness.
- Verify payment of official fees.

3.3. Technical Analysis

- Evaluate distinctiveness requirements.
- Check for conflicts with previously registered trademarks.
- Analyze classification within product/service classes.
- Record partial and final technical reports (performed by the examiner).

3.4. Issuance of Office Actions

- Generate formal requests for additional information to the applicant.
- Record documental or technical issues.
- Manage response deadlines.

3.5. Decision

- Approve the application based on AI-supported analysis.
- Refuse the application (with a justifiable explanation) based on AI-supported analysis.
- Archive the application due to lack of response or inconsistencies.

3.6. Final Grant

- Generate the final registration document.
- Publish relevant information.
- Provide a digital certificate.